

Psychopathological Factors, Lifestyle, and Well-Being in Obese Patients Undergoing Bariatric Surgery

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1. ABSTRACT

1.1. Background: Symptoms of depression and anxiety are frequently observed during the preoperative period of bariatric surgery and may be associated with patients' overall health status and well-being.

1.2. Objective: To investigate the association between psychopathological symptoms, lifestyle, and well-being in obese patients receiving care at a bariatric surgery outpatient clinic in a public teaching hospital.

1.3. Methods: This was a cross-sectional observational study. Mental health was assessed using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS). Health status indicators included Physical Activity Level (PAL), sedentary time, and body composition. Well-being was evaluated through a composite scale measuring sleep quality, distress, fatigue, and muscle pain. Associations were analyzed using linear and multinomial regression models (both crude and adjusted), with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

1.4. Results: A total of 186 patients participated in the study, of whom 170 (91.4%) were women, with a mean age of 45.56 ± 12.40 years. In the adjusted models, insufficient PAL (<150 minutes/week) was significantly associated with increased odds of depressive symptoms (OR = 3.51, 95% CI: 1.22–8.18), anxiety (OR = 3.36, 95% CI: 1.22–7.24), and stress (OR = 2.83, 95% CI: 1.11–7.41). High or very high distress levels were also significantly associated with anxiety ($p = 0.021$) and stress symptoms ($p = 0.002$). Furthermore, Two-Step Cluster analysis revealed that patients with lower well-being scores had significantly higher odds of being classified with severe or very severe mental health symptoms ($p \leq 0.01$).

1.5. Conclusion: In this sample of patients from a public teaching hospital, poorer mental health—characterized by symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress—was associated with insufficient physical activity and reduced well-being.

2. KEYWORDS: Bariatric surgery; Obesity; Anxiety; Depression; Stress; Lifestyle; Physical Activity.

3. INTRODUCTION

Obesity is defined as the excessive accumulation of body fat [1] and is recognized as a complex, multifactorial, and chronic non-communicable disease [2,3]. In terms of mental health, obesity has been associated with increased symptoms of anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem [4, 5, 6]. Bariatric Surgery (BS) is one of the most effective strategies for reducing body fat and is also linked to reductions in morbidity and mortality, as well as improvements in emotional health—especially when guided by appropriate professional monitoring [7]. Higher Body Mass Index (BMI) has been linked to a greater likelihood of experiencing depressive, anxious, and stress-related symptoms [8]. It is hypothesized that mental health outcomes in bariatric patients are influenced by both physical and behavioral factors. Behavioral aspects play a significant role in the multidimensional health of this population. For example, in a study comparing Physical Activity Levels (PAL) and emotional factors, patients showed increased PAL and reduced symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress following surgery [9]. In addition to PAL, sedentary time and sleep are considered 24-hour movement behaviors (24h-MB), which are important health-related variables. These behaviors can contribute to energy imbalance and excessive fat accumulation [10].

In the preoperative phase of BS, it is essential to assess not only physical health parameters but also emotional, psychosocial, and well-being indicators [11]. Well-being is defined as a state of personal satisfaction in which individuals feel good both physically and emotionally [12]. The literature highlights that the most frequently diagnosed conditions during the preoperative period include depression, anxiety, and binge eating disorder—all of which have a significant impact on patients' well-being and quality of life [13].

Given this context, and recognizing the importance of understanding how behavioral patterns, body composition, and well-being affect the mental health of individuals seeking BS, this study aimed to investigate the association between health and well-being correlates and mental health outcomes in patients attending a bariatric surgery outpatient clinic at a public university hospital.

Given the current context and the importance of investigating the influence of behavioral factors, body composition, and well-being on the mental health of patients seeking BS, this study aimed to investigate the association between psychopathological symptoms, health status, and well-being in obese patients receiving care at a bariatric surgery outpatient clinic in a public teaching hospital.

4. METHODS

4.1. Study design

This was a cross-sectional, analytical, and associative study conducted with patients followed by the Physical Education team at the Bariatric Surgery Outpatient Clinic (AMBCB) of the Hospital de Clínicas, Federal University of Triângulo Mineiro (HC-UFTM). Consultations took place between May 2023 and September 2024.

4.2. Sample and sampling procedures

The minimum sample size was estimated based on a finite population of 400 bariatric patients registered at HC-UFTM. The calculation considered a 4.38% prevalence of bariatric surgeries performed in Brazil [14], a power of 90%, a design effect of 2.0, and a 5% margin of error. For a 95% confidence level, a minimum of 110 participants was required. Sample size was calculated using StatCalc software, EpiInfo™ version 7.2.6.0 (Georgia, USA, 2021). To ensure the quality of reporting, the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) checklist for observational studies was followed.

4.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

All patients attending consultations were invited to participate. Eligibility criteria included: being in the preoperative phase, voluntarily agreeing to participate, being under regular follow-up at AMBCB, and having no physical or psychological limitations that would prevent participation in the evaluations—verified via medical reports accessed through the Hospital Information System of HC-UFTM. Patients who had been infected with COVID-19, did not complete all study procedures, or developed any physical or psychiatric condition during the process were excluded.

Participants who met the eligibility criteria signed the Informed Consent Form (ICF). The study protocol was approved by the HC-UFTM Research Ethics Committee under CAAE: 63185922.5.0000.8667, opinion number 5.695.381.

4.4. Data collection procedures

Patient assessments were conducted on the same day as their Physical Education consultation at AMBCB. After signing the ICF, data collection began with baseline information, followed by a physical evaluation, including anthropometric measurements and bioimpedance analysis. Subsequently, questions regarding well-being and daily behaviors were asked, including physical activity level (PAL), screen time (ST), sitting time (SitT), and sleep duration. This initial part was conducted in an interview format by trained Physical Education professionals to ensure standardized data collection. The mental health questionnaire was self-administered.

5. ASSESSMENT TOOLS

5.1. Symptoms of Anxiety, Depression and Stress

The Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21), short version translated and validated by Vignola (2013), was used to assess mental health symptoms. This instrument consists of 21 items, divided into three subscale ones (seven items each). Responses range from 0 ("Did not apply to me at all") to 3 ("Applied to me very much or most of the time"). Cut-off points for depression were: normal (0–4), mild (5–6), moderate (7–10), severe (11–13), and extremely severe (14+). For anxiety: normal (0–3), mild (4–5), moderate (6–7), severe (8–9), and extremely severe (10+). For stress: normal (0–7), mild (8–9), moderate (10–12), severe (13–16), and extremely severe (17+) (Martins et al., 2019). Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with values ≥ 0.800 considered high [15].

5.2. Well-Being

The Well-Being Scale (WBS) by Hooper et al. [16] was used to assess subjective well-being based on fatigue, muscle soreness, sleep quality, and stress perception over the past month. Each item was rated on a 7-point Likert scale. The total score was calculated by summing all items; higher scores indicated poorer well-being.

5.3. Lifestyle

Body composition was assessed following standards from the International Society for the Advancement of Kinanthropometry [17]. Weight and height were measured using a mechanical digital scale with an integrated stadiometer (Balmak Premium BK-F/FA®, São Paulo, Brazil; capacity: 200 kg, precision: 50 g). BMI (kg/m^2) and body composition were measured via octopolar bioelectrical impedance (InBody S10), which provided percentage of body fat (%BF) and muscle mass (kg).

Physical activity level was assessed using the short form of the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), which recorded time spent walking, performing moderate and vigorous physical activity (MVPA), as well as screen time (ST) and sitting time (SitT) on weekdays and weekends [18]. Individuals who reported ≥ 150 minutes of weekly physical activity were classified as sufficiently active [19].

5.4. Adjustment Variables

Sociodemographic characteristics and body image were considered adjustment variables in multivariate analyses. Data collected included sex, age (<40 years or ≥ 40 years), and body dissatisfaction, measured by the Silhouette Scale by Kakeshita et al. [20]. Dissatisfaction was calculated by subtracting the ideal silhouette from the current one selected by the participant.

5.5. Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 21.0 (IBM Corp®, New York, USA). Data normality was assessed via the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, skewness, kurtosis, and histogram inspection. Descriptive statistics for quantitative variables included mean, median, standard deviation (SD), and interquartile range. Categorical variables were presented as absolute and relative frequencies, using tables or charts [21].

Simple and multiple logistic regressions were conducted to assess associations between explanatory variables and the outcomes of depression, anxiety, and stress symptoms. For these analyses, DASS-21 outcomes were dichotomized into “no symptoms” and “with symptoms” to improve statistical power and interpretability of both crude and adjusted models. Results were reported using beta coefficients (β), crude and adjusted odds ratios (OR), 95% confidence intervals (CI), and p-values.

Variables with a p-value <0.20 in the crude model were included in the adjusted model using a backward stepwise method. Variables with lower significance were removed one by one until the best-fitting model was achieved. Model fit was assessed using the Hosmer & Lemeshow test and Pearson’s chi-square (χ^2), with p-values ≥ 0.05 indicating good fit.

To better understand the relationship between well-being and mental health, the explanatory variable “well-being” was grouped using Two-Step Cluster (TSC) analysis. The clustering variables—sleep quality, stress, fatigue, and muscle pain—were categorized as Very Good/Good, Regular, and Very Poor/Poor. Cluster selection was based on the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), highest predictor importance (close to 1), and optimal cohesion and separation.

The association between clustered “Well-Being” and “Mental Health” outcomes was tested using adjusted multinomial logistic regression. Mental health variables (depression, anxiety, stress) were categorized into “no symptoms,” “mild/moderate symptoms,” and “severe/very severe symptoms.” The final model was adjusted for sex and body dissatisfaction. Model fit was verified using the Hosmer & Lemeshow test, and adjusted ORs with 95% CIs were reported as measures of effect.

6. RESULTS

A total of 224 patients participated in the study. Of these, 38 were excluded: eight for not signing the informed consent form (ICF), ten due to complications related to COVID-19, and twenty for not completing all data collection procedures. Thus, 186 Bariatric Surgery (BS) patients were included in the analysis, of whom 170 (91.4%) were women, with a mean age of 45.56 (± 12.40) years, mean weight of 115.21 (± 17.74) kg, and mean BMI of 47.47 (± 7.26) kg/m².

According to the psychopathological assessment using the DASS, the classification of "severe/extremely severe" was observed in 23.5% for depression, 31.9% for anxiety, and 25% for stress.

Regarding the well-being domains, 42.9% of participants reported very high or high psychological distress. For fatigue, 40.3% rated it as regular, and half of the participants (50.4%) described muscle pain as very high or high. These findings suggest that both emotional and physical discomfort are prevalent in the daily lives of these patients.

As for body composition, 76.5% of patients were classified as having Class III obesity, and 74.8% were considered insufficiently active (<150 minutes of MVPA per week) according to national recommendations. In addition, sedentary time (ST) and total screen time (TT) were elevated in 64.7% and 58% of patients, respectively.

The results of the crude binary logistic regression analysis are presented in Table 1. Regarding depression, insufficient MVPA, higher distress scores, fatigue, and muscle pain were associated with symptom occurrence. For anxiety, the multivariate model included MVPA classification, sleep quality, distress, fatigue, and pain, while screen time was the only variable not associated. Finally, for stress, the well-being variables—sleep, distress, and pain—were all significantly associated with symptom presence.

Table 1: Crude Binary Logistic Regression Analysis Between Mental Health Factors and Explanatory Variables.

Variables	No symptoms vs. Depression symptoms			No symptoms vs. Anxiety symptoms			Sem sintomas versus com sintomas de estresse		
	OR	95%CI	p	OR	95%CI	p	OR	95%CI	p
Sufficient MVPA	1			1			1		
Insufficient MVPA	3.93	1.5-10.1	0.005*	1.94	0.8-4.5	0.124**	2.375	0.9-5.6	0.052**
Adequate ST	1			1			1		
High ST (≥ 250 min)	1.37	0.6-2.9	0.417	1.96	0.9-4.2	0.085**	1.6	0.75-3.4	0.224
Adequate Screen Time	1			1			1		
High Screen Time \geq (4h)	1.51	0.7-3.1	0.274	1.6	0.7-3.3	0.218	2.069	0.9-4.3	0.054*
Sleep – VG/G	1			1			1		
Sleep – Regular	0.86	0.3-2.0	0.738	2.25	0.9-5.3	0.068**	2.455	0.9-6.0	0.051**
Sleep – VP/P	1.33	0.5-3.3	0.547	3.29	1.2-8.9	0.019*	7.67	2.6-22.1	p<0.001*
Stress – VG/G	1			1			1		
Stress – Regular	2.19	0.6-6.9	0.186**	4.42	1.3-14.0	0.012*	4.872	1.2-18.7	0.022
Stress - VH/H	6.8	2.1-21.5	0.001*	13.9	4.1-46.9	p<0.001*	16.74	4.2-65.4	p<0.001*
Fatigue – VG/G	1			1			1		

Fatigue - R	0.89	0.3-2.3	0.82	1.75	0.6-4.6	0.254	0.9	0.37-2.5	0.957
Fatigue - VH/H	2.05	0.7-5.4	0.152**	4.22	1.5-11.8	0.006*	2.472	0.9-6.6	0.073**
Pain – VG/G	1			1			1		
Pain - R	2.25	0.7-7.0	0.164**	3.09	0.9-9.6	0.053**	3.953	1.2-13.0	0.024*
Pain– VH/H	3.06	1.0-8.9	0.042*	7.5	2.4-22.8	p<0.001*	4.185	1.5-12.9	0.013*

Abbreviations: MVPA = Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity; ST = Sitting time; Screen Time = Time spent using screens; VG/G = Very good / Good; R = Regular; VH/H = Very high / High; VP/P = Very poor / Poor.

Crude logistic regression: *p < 0.05; **p ≤ 0.200.

Based on the variables analyzed in the crude model, it was possible to observe the odds ratios for the occurrence and classification of symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress in the adjusted multivariate model (Table 2).

Patients with insufficient MVPA had 3.51 times greater odds (95% CI: 1.22–8.18) of being classified with some level of depressive symptoms. Furthermore, participants with insufficient MVPA and very high/high distress had 3.36 (95% CI: 1.22–7.24) and 6.36 (95% CI: 1.31–30.76) times greater odds, respectively, of presenting anxiety symptoms.

Table 2: Adjusted Multivariate Binary Logistic Regression of Explanatory Variables Associated with the Classification of Symptoms Assessed by DASS-21.

Variáveis [#]	“No depression symptoms” versus “With depression symptoms”				
	β	OR	IC95%		p
MVPA sufficient	1				
MVPA in sufficient	1.389	3.51	1.22	8.18	0.002*
Hosmer and Lemeshow test (χ ²)	p = 0.982 (χ ² : 0.509)				
	“No anxiety symptoms” versus “With anxiety symptoms”				
	β	OR	IC95%		p
MVPA sufficient	1				
MVPA insufficient	1.54	3.36	1.22	7.24	0.001*
Stress – Very low/low	1				
Stress - Regular	0.651	1.918	0.449	8.202	0.38
Stress – Very high/high	1.85	6.36	1.315	30.759	0.021*
Hosmer and Lemeshow test (χ ²)	p = 0.996 (χ ² : 1.255)				
	“No stress symptoms” versus “With stress symptoms”				
	β	OR	IC95%		p
MVPA sufficient	1				
MVPA insufficient	1.345	2.83	1.11	7.46	0.005*
Stress – Very low/low	1				
Stress - Regular	0.759	2.136	0.65	7.023	0.211
Stress - Muito high/high	1.89	6.621	2.018	21.723	0.002*
Hosmer and Lemeshow test (χ ²)	p = 0.856 (χ ² : 1.332)				

MVPA: Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity; β: Regression coefficient; OR: Odds ratio; Pearson’s χ² test: Goodness-of-fit. Adjustment variables: Age, sex, and body dissatisfaction.

Finally, physically inactive bariatric patients and those classified with very high/high distress had 2.83 (95% CI: 1.11–7.41) and 6.62 (95% CI: 2.018–21.723) times greater odds, respectively, of presenting stress symptoms. These findings suggest that both physical inactivity and negative distress classification—particularly related to stress—may be influential factors in the development of mental health symptoms.

All multivariate models demonstrated good fit, as indicated by the Hosmer and Lemeshow test, with Pearson’s chi-square test p-values greater than 0.05.

To complete the analysis of the results, we tested whether overall well-being was associated with the classifications of anxiety, depression, and stress. Therefore, the variables sleep, distress, fatigue, and muscle pain were grouped using TSC analysis.

The TSC profile analysis identified the optimal model with the best fit indicators: the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC = 1432), a ratio of the largest to smallest cluster size of 1.11, and a silhouette coefficient of 0.4, indicating moderate cohesion and separation. This model revealed three distinct classes:

“Better well-being” (n = 43; 35.3%), “Regular well-being” (n = 38; 31.8%), and “Worse well-being” (n = 39; 32.8%).

Based on the response frequencies presented in Figure 1, the “Better well-being” class showed higher proportions of responses classified as “Very good/good” or “Very low/low” for sleep, distress, fatigue, and muscle pain. In contrast, in the “Worse well-being” class, most responses were concentrated in the “Very poor/poor” or “Very high/high” categories. The “Regular well-being” class displayed intermediate patterns between the two extremes. In all these domains, the association was confirmed using the Linear-by-Linear Association test ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 1: Two-Step Cluster analysis of well-being classification.

* The pain information refers to muscle pain, according to the Well-Being Scale by Hooper et al. [16].

Finally, an association was found between the multivariate well-being model and the classifications of “asymptomatic,” “mild/moderate,” and “severe/very severe” symptoms in the DASS-21 domains. The TSC analysis revealed that patients grouped into the “Regular WB” and “Worst WB” clusters had 3.89 (95% CI: 1.23–12.29) and 8.33 (95% CI: 2.33–29.72) times higher odds, respectively, of exhibiting mild/moderate anxiety symptoms ($p = 0.001$) (Table 3). Regarding stress ($p = 0.013$), patients classified as “Worst WB” had 4.14 times higher odds (95% CI: 1.34–12.72) of presenting mild/moderate symptoms.

Moreover, patients in the AMBCB group showed 42.7% (95% CI: 1.33–13.06), 76.5% (95% CI: 1.89–17.99), and 85.1% (95% CI: 1.96–20.62) higher odds of exhibiting “severe/very severe” symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress, respectively, compared to those in the “Best WB” cluster (Table 3).

These findings suggest that well-being—particularly among patients classified as having “Worst WB”—is associated with a greater susceptibility to symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress.

Table 3: Association Between Well-Being and the Multinomial Classification of depression, anxiety, and stress symptoms.

Well-Being classification	No depression symptoms versus <i>Light/Moderate depression</i>				No depression symptoms versus <i>Very Severe/Severe depression</i>					
	β	OR	IC95%		p	β	OR	IC95%		p^{**}
Best	1					1				
Regular	-0.73	0.93	0.325	2.659	0.892	0.282	1.326	0.387	4.544	0.654
Worst	0.31	1.364	0.459	4.052	0.577	1.427	4.167	1.329	13.065	0.014*
	No anxiety symptoms versus <i>Light/Moderate anxiety</i>				No anxiety symptoms ANS versus <i>Very Severe/Severe anxiety</i>					
	β	OR	IC95%		p	β	OR	IC95%		P^*
Best	1					1				
Regular	1.358	3.889	1.23	12.292	0.021*	0.31	1.364	0.459	4.052	0.577
Worst	2.12	8.333	2.336	29.723	0.001*	1.765	5.844	1.898	17.997	0.002*
	No stress symptoms versus <i>Light/Moderate stress</i>				No stress symptoms ANS versus <i>Very Severe/Severe stress</i>					
	β	OR	IC95%		p	β	OR	IC95%		p
Best	1					1				
Regular	0.896	2.45	0.865	6.939	0.092	-0.069	0.933	0.233	3.744	0.922
Worst	1.42	4.136	1.345	12.721	0.013*	1.851	6.364	1.963	20.625	0.002*

* $p \leq 0.05$; β : regression coefficient; ** multinomial regression based on the Two-Step Cluster analysis; OR: odds ratio; CI: confidence interval.

7. DISCUSSION

Overall, patients who self-rated their well-being as poor and did not meet the minimum PAL recommendation of 150 minutes per week presented worse symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress. Excess weight can lead to multiple consequences for an individual's health, including mental health. Psychological suffering may result in mood dysregulation, which can lead to compulsive eating or self-harm [22]. Therefore, assessing and monitoring emotional aspects in patients undergoing bariatric surgery (BS), both before and after the procedure, is essential for promoting health and preventing complications. It is recommended that bariatric candidates undergo psychological evaluations as part of the surgical process. The three most common psychological diagnoses in the preoperative period are depression, anxiety, and binge eating disorder—findings consistent with this study, in which anxiety was the most prevalent severe or very severe symptom measured by the DASS-21[23].

According to the National Health Survey (PNS), more than half of the Brazilian population (60.3%) is overweight—62.6% of women and 57.5% of men. Obesity prevalence was 21.8% in men and 29.5% in women [24]. A systematic review on the effects of ovarian hormones on adipose tissue found that estrogen significantly contributes to increased obesity in women [25]. Another review on the relationship between obesity and depression in women indicated that emotional factors contribute to obesity development, while excess weight also increases depressive symptoms, especially in middle-aged women due to hormonal [26]. Moreover, concerns about body image and experiences of stigma and prejudice are more prevalent among women [27].

VIGITEL data also indicate that women (36.2%) engage in less leisure-time physical activity than men (45.8%) [28].

As shown earlier, BS candidates often present with symptoms of depression and anxiety, largely due to excessive body fat [29]. However, beyond obesity, insufficient moderate to vigorous physical activity (MVPA) may negatively impact mental health. In this study, 74.8% of participants were physically inactive (<150 minutes/week), and inactivity was associated with all three DASS symptoms (depression, anxiety, and stress). Literature shows that physical activity is effective in reducing these symptoms. Clark et al. [30] found that physical activity reduced the likelihood of depressive and anxiety symptoms in BS candidates. Reaching recommended PA levels may therefore improve emotional well-being and overall quality of life in these patients [31].

Regarding well-being, high/very high stress (42.9%) and high/very high muscle pain (50.4%) were the most prevalent indicators. Health is defined not only by the absence of disease but as a complete state of physical, mental, and social well-being [32]. According to the “Informa em Ação” project, well-being is a personal state of satisfaction influenced by social relationships, diet, sleep, and leisure-time activities.

Musculoskeletal pain is common in BS candidates, primarily due to excess body weight [33]. Basem et al. [34] showed that individuals with higher BMI had significantly higher pain levels. Stress also has many links with obesity, such as affecting cognition, increasing caloric intake, reducing PA, and impairing sleep quality [35]. Stress is defined as a global, complex reaction of the organism that includes physical, psychological, mental, and hormonal components [36]. Psychological stress contributes to emotional distress. Guerrini-Usubini et al. [37], using the DASS-21, demonstrated that higher emotional dysregulation led to greater psychological suffering, increased food intake, and consequently, weight gain.

TSC analysis and multinomial regression showed that participants with lower well-being were more likely to experience symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress. These findings support existing literature indicating that excess body fat impacts not only physical but also mental health and quality of life. Mental health, quality of life, and obesity subtypes are closely linked. Even metabolically healthy individuals with obesity may present mental health issues and reduced quality of life (Kim, Kim, & Song, 2020). A review by Abiri et al. [38] also found that when metabolic disorders are present, the risk of mental health problems and poor quality of life increases. Hence, psychological assessment and continuous support should be part of the care provided to bariatric patients.

This study has some limitations. Lifestyle variables such as PA, sedentary behavior, and screen time were measured using self-report questionnaires. However, in a clinical outpatient setting with an epidemiological design, the IPAQ was a practical and validated tool for the Brazilian population. Mental health was also assessed through a self-report instrument. Nevertheless, the DASS-21 is widely used and validated in Brazil. Internal consistency was confirmed with high Cronbach’s alpha values: depression = 0.895, stress = 0.852, and anxiety = 0.890 [39].

This study presents novel and important findings regarding the mental health of BS candidates, highlighting the need for regular monitoring throughout the surgical process. It used a representative sample of patients from a public university hospital and examined the relationship between health behaviors and mental health in the Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS). Psychological disorders are among the fastest-growing health issues worldwide, especially in people with obesity [40]. Multivariate and cluster analyses in this study allowed for

deeper evaluation of how different factors such as well-being, stress, and PA interact and impact mental health. This emphasizes the importance of comprehensive, multidisciplinary care.

The findings support the development of treatment strategies and health promotion initiatives aimed at improving well-being, reducing stress, and increasing physical activity. Finally, the role of physical education professionals is critical to help patients increase PA levels, reduce sedentary behavior, and improve well-being and stress management. Obesity is a multifactorial disease that can negatively impact physical, social, cognitive, and emotional health. Therefore, implementing structured physical activity programs for bariatric patients may serve as effective non-pharmacological interventions in the treatment, rehabilitation, and physical reconditioning of candidates for bariatric surgery.

8. CONCLUSION

The results of the present study showed that patients attending the bariatric surgery outpatient clinic exhibited higher levels of anxiety, psychological distress, grade III obesity, low levels of physical activity, and high sedentary behavior.

Statistical inferences indicated that physical inactivity and high distress were associated with symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress. Patients in this study experienced worse mental health associated with insufficient physical activity levels and lower overall well-being. Specifically, low or insufficient physical activity and poor well-being were the main factors associated with the classification of very severe/severe mental health symptoms.

Cluster analysis (TSC) revealed that patients from the BS outpatient clinic with poorer well-being—characterized by lower sleep quality, higher stress, fatigue, and muscle pain—were more likely to be classified with more severe mental health symptoms.

Further longitudinal and experimental studies are needed to confirm whether increasing physical activity and exercise levels, along with other body-based practices, can improve well-being and consequently reduce the incidence of severe depression, anxiety, and stress symptoms among patients preparing for or recovering from bariatric surgery.

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